

**Historical and Religious Tourism in Vindhya Region: Special focus
on Amarkantak, Chitrakoot, Khajuraho and Orchha
(Ancient, Medieval to Modern Periods)**

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A B S T R A C T

The highland of Vindhya Mountain designated as 'Vindhya region. Since the ancient time the region has been the centre of historical and religious places. Amarkantak is located in Maikal hill; the junctions of Vindhya and Satpura, the place of origin of holy Narmada River. Its spiritual and historical importance has been recorded in Purans and Sanskrit literatures. The Hindu Lord Shri Rama spent a considerable period of exile in Chitrakoot. This place credits 'Valmiki Ramayana' (Maharishi Valmiki) and 'Ramcharitra Manas' (Saint Tulsidas) writings. Chitrakoot is main destination place of 'Ram Van Gaman Pathway' tourist circuit. The Khajuraho temples built in the mediaeval century by Chandela's Dynasty, the UNESCO World Heritage sites of 'Khajuraho Group of Monuments' is famous for its Nagara-Style architecture and graceful sculptures of nayikas (Hindu Mythological female protagonists) and deities. Capital of Bundela's dynasty was the Orchha, is historical and religious place. Obviously, the Vindhya region enjoys a credible place of culture, mythology, history, architecture, sculptures from ancient, medieval to modern periods.

Key words: Vindhya region, History, Amarkantaka, Chitrakoot, Khajuraho, Orchha.

Introduction

The highland of Vindhya Mountain designated as ‘Vindhya Bhumi’ is situated in north-east part of Madhya Pradesh, India. Since the Pauranik era the region has been the centre of historical and religious places. This script denotes a brief account of historical and religious tourist places of Vindhya region and their mythological and architectural significance.

(1) Amarkantak: Amarkantak is a major religious place of Vindhya region, a junction place of Vindhya, Satpuda and Maikal mountains. Its height is 1060 meters. Its spiritual and historical importance has been recorded in Purans and Sanskrit literatures. According to Matsya Puran, Lord Shiva and Goddess Uma live here. Amarkantak is a place of meditation of sages like great Kapil Muni, Vyas, Bhrgu, Kabir etc. It is a place of origin of holy Narmada, seven famous rivers of India. The Sanskrit granth ‘Meghdoot’ was written here by Kalidas and ‘Shankha Darshan’ by sage Kapil Muni.

Table – 1: Historical and Religious Tourism in Vindhya Region of India

SN	Name of Place/ (District)	Religious & Historical Tourist Spots / Temples, Statues	Festivals/ Important Days	Nearest Railway Sta./ Aerodrome	Special Features/ Mythology, Legends
1	Amarkantaka (Anuppur)	Holy Narmada River Origin (Udgam),Narmada Temple, Kalchuri Temples Complex, Jwaleshwar Temple, Shri Yantra Mahameru temple, Sarvodaya Jain temple etc.	Narmada Jayanti, Shivratri, Makar Sankranti.	Anuppur/ Jabalpur	(1)Meeting point of Vindhya, Satpuda and Maikal Hills. (2)Origin point of holy Narmada, Son and Johila Rivers.
2.	Chitrakoot (Satna)	Kamadgiri, Bharat Milap Temple, Ramghat, Janki Kund, Sphatic Shila, Atri-Ansuya Ashram, Maharishi Valmiki Ashram , Sage	Deepawali, Sharad Poornima, Ramnavami, Amavasya	Chitrakoot/Allahabad(Prayagraj)	(1)Hindu Lord Rama spent a considerable period of exile. (2)The place credits ‘Valmiki Ramayana’ and

		Sharbhanga and Sutikshna Ashrams, Ganesh Bagh etc.			‘Ramcharitra Manas’ writings.
3.	Khajuraho (Chhatarpur) (a)Western Group: (b)Eastern Group: (c) Southern Group:	KandariyaMahadeo,Lakshman,Matangeshwar ,Chitragupt, Jagdamba, ChausathYogini, Vishwanath temples etc. Brahma, Vaman, Jawari, AdinathParswanath, temples etc. Chaturbhuj, Dulha deo temples	Khajuraho Dance Festival (in March), Shivratri, Ramnavmi, Deepawali	Khajuraho, Satna / Khajuraho	(1) Nagara – Style Architecture. (2)Panchayatana Temples (Five- Shrine Complex). (3)Under UNESCO World Heritage Sites.
4.	Orchha (Niwari)	Orchha Fort Complex,Jahangir Palace, Ram Raja Temple, Chaturbhuj Temple, Cenotaphas.	Ramnavmi, Dashhra, Deepawali	Jhansi / Gwalior	Ex-capital of Bundela dynasty situated in the bank of Betwa River.

Important Spots of Amarkantak

(i) Narmada Temples:

There are two temples opposite each other connected by a porch and named as ‘Narmada Origin Temple’ and ‘Narmada Temple’, each Temple has a female idol, one idol has 4 arms and the other idol of 8 arms. Devotees worship mainly these idols.

(ii) Narmada Circumabulation (Parikrma):

It is a ritual journey carrying a great importance in Hindus. The pilgrim performs it along the left side of Narmada River (keeping it at right of the performer) without crossing the river. It starts either from the origin of Narmada or from the Omkareshwar and ends accordingly at the same place taking a total of 3 years, 3 months and 13 days period in pieces. All pilgrim places and ghats in route are seen by the performer. In addition to the Dharmshalas, locals along the

route also extend their hospitality. Some pilgrims complete it even in 180 days. Complete journey from Amarkantak (Narmada Kund) and its termination in Gujarat (Mithi Talai) to and fro involves approximately 2624 km. It is performed ritually and provide the holy darshan of places like Omkareshwar, Maheshwar, Mamleshwar, Bhedaghat etc. In ancient time the first journey is credited to Maharishi Markandeya.

(iii) Ancient Temples of the Amarkantak:

Ancient Temples of the Kalachuri period are one of the prominent heritage sites in Vindhya region of Central India, were constructed under the supervision of Kalachuri King Karnadeva during the 11th century CE. They reflect the sheer brilliance of the Kalachuri architecture. Today the Kalachuri Temple complex is a protected monument under the Archaeological Survey of India and the complex is very well maintained with manicured lawns and landscape gardening. The complex consists of six temples and a kund named Suraj Kund.

(a) The Karna Temple popularly known as Trimukhi Temple, is the largest and the most prominent temple in the complex which is crowned with a towering ornate sikhara. It was built by King Lakshmikarna (1041-1073 CE). The temple consists of three shrines built over a raised platform which can be accessed through a flight of steps.

(b) Machchendranath Temple: Kalchuri king of Tripuri Karnadeo got this temple constructed in Nagara style structure during 11th century. This Shiva temple has sanctum, vestibule and mandapa in columns. Vestibule has “Sukhnsi” with lion statue at the top. The top of sanctum has Shikara Nagara crowned with Amalkas and Kalasha.

(c) Pataleshwar Temple is dedicated to Lord Shiva It is said that Adi Sankaracharya installed Shiva Linga in this temple during his visit in the 8th century CE. However, the temple was built (1041-1073 CE). The superstructure over the mandapa is pyramidal. The vestibule has a superstructure called sukhanasi. The sanctum is built on Pancha Ratha's plan. The floor of the sanctum is 1.4 meters below when compared to the floor of the mandapa. Hence, the temple is called Pataleshwar Temple.

(d) Keshava Narayan Temple dedicated to Lord Vishnu, was built by Bhonsle ruler of Nagpur, during the 18th century. It consists of two shrines connected to a common mandapa via

vestibule. Both the shrines are situated perpendicular to each other. One shrine is facing towards the east while the other shrine is facing towards the north. The shikara over the sanctums follows the Nagara style. There are niches on the three sides of the sanctum.

(e) Panch Math is a group of five temples constructed over a raised platform in different architectural styles. These temples were built by Gond rulers in the 15th century CE. The shikara over the sanctum follows Nagara style.

(f) The Johila Temple is considered as the latest structure in this complex, is constructed by Baghel King's of Rewa in 19th century CE. Built on a raised platform, the shikara of the temple follows a pyramidal style adorned by side transepts on all sides.

(g) According to legend, Shankaracharya built the Suraj Kund in the 8th century CE, to specify the origin of holy Narmada River.

(h) Jwaleshwar Mahadeo Temple: It is dedicated to Lord Shiva. Closely is an origin of Johila river (3rd river of Amarkantaka). Mythologically this Shivling was established by Lord Shiva himself. Many more Shiv lingas were spread here in Maikal mountain, so this place called 'Maha Rudra Meru'.

(iv) Modern Period Temples:

(a) Sri Yantra Temple:

The Sri Yantra is a form of mystical diagram (Yantra). It consists of nine interlocking triangle – four upward one which represent Shiva, and five downward ones represent Shakti. All these surround the central point, the bindu . These triangles represent the cosmos and human body. Because of these nine triangles, Sri Yantra is also known as the 'Navayoni Chakra'. When the two-dimensional Sri Yantra represented three-time dimensions, it is called 'Mahameru'.

(b) Saryodaya Jain Temple:

Near the origin place of Narmada a new Saryodaya Jain Temple has been established and *Pran pratishtha* (consecration) performed between 25th March to 2nd April 2023, in four-acre area. Its height is 151 feet, built pink stone brought from Rajasthan using jiggery mixture. The cement and iron have not been used. The idol of Lord Adinath is made of *Astadhatu* weighting

24 tons seated in 28 tons lotus thus making a total weight of 52 tons and constitutes important Jain temple. Other idols of temple present unique carvings. (Ref.1-3).

(2) Chitrakoot:

Chitrakoot (chitra=wonderful, colourful; koot= hills) the term Chitrakoot denotes colored wonderful hills, which harbours numerous medicaments, where sages attain different levels of spiritualisation causing beneficial impact on world through their sadhana, yoga and tapasya (austerity). Sati Ansuiya, Dattatreya, Maharishi Markandeya, Sharbang, Sutikshna, Maharishi Valmiki and many other seers and thinkers have lived here through ages. Mythologically, Lord Rama, Sita and Lakshman spent considerable time here on their way to forest (Vanvash) for 14 years of exile. The stay in Chitrakoot resulted beneficially as they met several sages who guided and mentored them includes sage Atri and Ansuiya. Ansuiya blessed Sita that she will always be remembered as the epitome. Lord Rama met sage Bharadwas who preached Rama on devotion, scarifies and truth in addition to duties of king and right path.

This place credits ‘Valmiki Ramayana’ (Maharishi Valmiki) and ‘Ramcharitra Manas’ (Sant Tulsidas) writings. Chitrakoot is main destination place of “Ram Van Gaman Pathway” tourist circuit. This divine place has many sites of great religious importance like Kamadgiri, Bharat Milap Temple, Ramghat, Janki Kund, Sati Anusuiya Ashram, SphaticShila, Ram Saiya, Parn kuti, etc. near Chitrakoot Maharshi Valmiki Ashram, Rishi Sharbhang and Rishi Sutikshna ashrams are established. At Chitrakoot everything relates to Lord Rama.

Ganesh Bagh Chitrakoot:

A unique archaeological site Ganesh Bagh situated near some distance of Chitrakoot. It is built by King Vinayak Rao Peshwa in 1880s. The premises has an ornately carved Shiva temple with various unique features. These include a seven storey’s step well, a big pond with steps and cenotaphs around it, few more smaller enclosures, a palace, remains of few other buildings and wide-open space which is now being converted into lawns and gardens.

The seven-storey step well is the first structure after entering the gate. There was a narrow canal like opening through which deep down, water could be seen in a long stretch. In between, at regular distances, horizontal platforms connected verandahs of both the side. The

step well, it's structure, design and continuous presence of water all together form an amazing cooling system. The step well is an amazing feat of engineering in perfect synchronization with nature.

The Shiva temple is Panchayatan with Nagara style architecture stands on a raised platform. At one end of this covered colonnaded verandah are three chambers with stone door frames which are adorned beautifully carved images of various Gods and Goddesses. On some of these images' sea blue, pink, maroon colours still can be seen. No worship or daily rituals are performed here, but local people throng the temple during Shravan and on the occasion of Shivratri. The floor of the verandah running in front of these chambers is very interesting. Three type of indoor board games: Chaupar, Ashtapada/Solah Gotia and Gilharia Katawa were engraved on the floor, are a surprising. A few feet ahead the verandah lies an oval small pond shaped structure.

Reaching the rooftop one can even touch the ornately carved shikharas of temples. The richly carved shikharas display images of various gods, goddesses, mythological creatures, animals and some erotic figures too. This open rooftop was connected to the palace through passages. In front of the shikhara, on a small covered platform, sat Ganesha. That may be one reason that the temple is popular as a Ganesha temple among locals even though the main deity was Shiva.

Ganesh Bagh is the big pond near the temple, steps from all the four sides lead to water. The pond is square in shape, few cenotaphs around the pond were still intact. Ganesh Bagh is an ASI protected monument. (Ref.4-5).

(3) Khajuraho Group of Temples:

UNESCO World Heritage site of 'Khajuraho Group of Monuments' is famous for its wonderful exclusive architecture and graceful sculptures of Nayikas (Hindu Mythological protagonists) and deities. It was built during 950 to 1130 AD by Chandela dynasty and discovered by British Army Captain T.S. Burt during 1838 in the wild forests of Khajuraho, which count 85 out of which only 25 has been restored and divided into three groups namely Western, Eastern and Southern. The temple belongs to Lord Shiva (7), Vishnu (9), Sun (1), Devi

Chausath Yogini (1), Brahma (1), Hanuman (1), Devi Mahishasur Mardani (1) and Digambar Jain Tirthankars (4). The oldest one is of Chausath Yogini (9th century) and youngest Dulhadeo (1100-1130 AD).

Architecture:

The temple is built in Nagara style architecture. Though each structure is varying even that these present precise architectural principles of shape in form and orientation. Containing certain essential element like curvilinear shikara, a high raised platform, an entrance porch (mukh mandapa or ardh mandapa), a portico (mandapa), a vestibule (antrala) and inner sanctum (garbhgrih). Some larger temples also have walkway around the inner sanctum (pradakchhina path), large hall (mahamandapa), subsidiary shrines at each corner of platform complete Panchayatana temples. Majority of these temples are erecting in east-west axis resulting facilitating direct entry of rising sun. The architecture followed Vishwakarma school of “Vastushastra” tradition and simulate almost all Hindu temples. The design plan consists of Mandala (circle), Purusha and Vastu.

Sculpture Art:

The sculpture of temples is made of fine-grained stone varying from the pale buff to pink yellow and brown colours. The sculpture can be classified into eight categories: (i) The cult icons installed in sanctum. (ii) The attendant and surrounding divinities like that of the Asta-Dikpalas. (iii) The demi-god’s such as Vidhyadharas, Gandharvas, Yaaksh, Ganas. (iv) Celestial women called Apsaras, Sura-sundaries (Nayikas). (v) Amorphous couples of mithunas and erotic groups. (vi) Secular scenes depicting royal hunt, king at court, teacher and pupil, dancers and musicians, domestic scenes. (vii) Animal figures both mythical and real like sardulas or vyals, elephants, parrots, scorpions etc. (viii) Geometrical and floral design covered on ceiling on borders of panels and walls on pillars and elsewhere.

Interesting in Khajuraho:

(i) Shikaras: - When one entry at the Kandariya Mahadeo temple the individual should view shikaras or temple rooftop stimulating Himalayan abode of God.

- (ii) Sardula or Vyal Statue: -These statues represent four- lion stroking sardulas or part- lion, part human mythical beasts.
- (iii) Kama Sutra Carving: - There are several erotic carvings spread all over Khajuraho temples.
- (iv) Nandi Statue: - It's a massive 2.2m long statue of Nandi, the bull- vehicle of Lord Shiva facing Vishwanath temple. Its ultimate.
- (v) Vishnu's boar: - it's a 9th century statue of Varaha, the boar incarnation of Lord Vishnu. The beauty lies in the Bramanical gods and goddesses carved out all over.
- (vi) Apsaras and Sura-Sundaries: - They are graceful depictions of nymphs found all over Khajuraho Temples-
 - (a) Apsaras: - They are shown dancing in varies postures as attendants of the higher divinities, they are represented with hands folded or carrying the lotus- flower, mirror, water-jar, raiment's, ornaments etc, as offerings for the deities.
 - (b) Sura-Sundaries: - More frequently, sura-sundaries are portrayed expressing common human moods, emotions and activities and often difficult to distinguish from conventional human nayikas. They are, thus, shown disrobing, yawning scratching their backs, touching their breasts, rising water from wet plaits, removing thorns from their feet, fondling babies, playing with pets like parrots and monkeys, writing letters, playing on a flute or vina, painting designs on walls or bedecking themselves in various ways by painting their feet, or applying collyrium to their eyes.

The Secrecy of Copulatory Idols in Khajuraho:

The carvings of copulatory idol at the walls and gate of temples in Khajuraho emphasize on philosophical view specifying the sex and spirituality are part of life. Since the sanctum of temple lodges, the idol of God, obviously it emphasizes that one has to get rid of sex to attain the knowledge of God. Lord Shiva is considered the father of sexy world acknowledging in the Shiva temples are decorated externally by copulatory idols in the walls and door. During the middle era the uncovered chest was considered a symbol of beauty. The controller of world, is the God (male) and the whole world, the nature. The God and nature collectively constitute the

universe. Conclusively the idols of God in and sanctum and nacked cum copulatory idol carvings on walls emphasize the creation of nature.

Important Temples of Khajuraho:

(i) Kandariya Mahadeo Temple- Amongst the Khajuraho temples Kandariya Mahadeo temple belongs to Lord Shiva is the largest and tallest temple (31meter) with the apex simulating Kailash Mountain. The linga (vigrah) of Lord Shiva is of marble. Varying idols carved (800) and uncarved (600) present here.

(ii) Lakshman Temple - Lakshman temple is one amongst the largest temple of Khajuraho devoted to lord Vishnu. It is most famous and walls are carved with many idols. (Rebirth of lord Vishnu) some sexy structures, elephants and cavalry figures.

(iii)Matangeshwar Temple: It's a temple of Lord Shiva.Lord Shiva is equated to saint Matang.It's a planned architect bearing beautiful lord Shiva. Due to its form ASI has recognized it as national monument. This is only temple where devotees perform worship.

(iv) Devi Jagdamba Temple: It pertains to Lord Shiva and Parvati. It is famous for beautiful sexy idols and attractive band carvings. The sanctum of goddess Parvati is attractive. Many carvings of men and women pairs, beautiful female are present.

(v) Chitragupt Temple: Chitragupt Temple is a Hindu temple devoted to Lord Sun. It has decorative carvings. It has as octagonal roof and bears 10 idols of lord of different avatar (appearances), other carvings match as in above temples.

(vi) Adinath Temple: It is a famous Jain temple devoted to Jain tirthankar Adinath. The walls have carvings of Hindu god and goddess like Yachhni, Chakreshwari, Ambika, Garud and lord Adinath seated on a lotus.

(vii) Chaturbhuj Temple: This too is devoted to lord Vishnu bearing 4 hands on a high dias. The temple as carvings of lord Bramha,Shiva and Vishnu along with idols of beautiful ladies of the era. (Ref.6-11).

(4) Orchha: Orchha is a historical place of Vindhya region, situated in the bank of Betwa river. It was capital of Bundela dynasty in medieval period. The Jahangir Palace, Raj Palace and

Sheesh Mahal are the three sections of Orchha Palace Complex. The palaces have an introverted courtyard type of architectural plan with some innovative changes. The blend of Mughal and Bundela style of architecture is really appreciable for its harmony, intelligent engineering and magnificent building. Jahangir palace built by king Veer Singh Bundela in 1605 AD in honour of Mughal Emperor Jahangir. It is a fine example of harmonious visual language of Indo-Islamic style monument, built with red and yellow sand stone. Palace is square in plan with four bastions of each corner with eight topped domes. It is three storied palaces with a fountain in the center. The ceremonial gateway of the place is east facing is traditional and artistic grandiose.

Two stone elephants guard at the entrance stairway with ringing bells for the announcement of king arrival. The Bundela school of paintings portrays the true 'Bundeli culture' of medieval periods, the lovely court scene and the daily life of the royal's and the citizen in walls and ceiling of the palace. Ram Raja Temple Orchha, is the only place where the Lord Ram is worshipped as a King. Interestingly, not just worshipped as a king here 'Guard of Honour' (gun salutes) are also offered as a mark of devotion and respect. Chaturbhuj Temple is dedicated to Lord Vishnu. The temple is a multistoried structure with the features of temple, fort and palace. This temple has 344 feet Viman which is one of the highest Viman among the Hindu temples. Lotus emblem and other symbol of religious significance provide the delicate exterior ornamentation. The temple was constructed in 1558 to 1573AD by king Madhukar Shah Bundela.

The Cenotaphs (Chhartis) of Orchha were constructed in honour of its erstwhile rulers of Bundela dynasty. Fourteen stone cenotaphs are located along the Kanchan ghat of Betwa river representing the most scenic beauty. Most of them are multistoried designed in Nagar Panchayatna style. Cenotaph of king Veer Singh Dev has Islamic features like large domes and strong pillars. (Ref.12-13).

Conclusively the Vindhya region enjoys a credible place of culture, beliefs, mythology, history, architecture, sculptures, eco-tourism from ancient, medieval to modern periods.

Reference:

1. Kumar Santosh (2021): Circumambulation in Indian pilgrimage: Meaning and Manifestation. *Int. Nat. Jour. of Scientific and Engineering Research*, Vol. 12(1) pp. 232-243
2. Saxena Saurabh (2022): Amarkantaka- The Pride of Maikal. *Puratattva*.Sept13,2022. putrtattva.in/amarkantaka/
3. ShahajiShovakar (2022) : Show casing the significance of river in Indian culture: Especially the Narmada River. *Innovation the Research Concept* Vol.8 (8) (<http://www.socialresearchfoundation.com/innovation.php#8>).
4. Singh Vikas and Gujar C.P.(2022): Historical and religious places of rural tourism in Chitrakoot region. *Int.Nat. Jour.of Creative Research Thought(IJCRT)*,Vol. 10 (11) pp.a1-a9.
5. Uppadhyay M.K. (2014) :*Chitrakoot: An Archaeo-Religious Study*. Kaveri Books . pp. 96.
6. Bajpai A. (2017) : Review on the Architecture of Khajuraho Temples. *Int. Nat. Jour. of Applied Research*, Vol. 3(6) pp. 1450-1453.
7. Desai Devangana (2003) :*Khajuraho*. Oxford University Press, pp. 1-124.
8. Dhama B.L. (1927) :*A Guide to Khajuraho*. Times of India Press Bombay. pp. 1-68.
9. Krisna Deva (2002): *Khajuraho (World Heritage Series)*. Pub. by Archaeological Survey of India. PP.1- 194. (<https://archive.org/Khajurahoookris>).
10. Nath R. (2004) :*Temple and Erotic Art of Khajuraho*. Roopa Publication Delhi. pp. 1-96.
11. Singh Sharad (2011): Mystery of mithun idol of Khajuraho. *A Mirror of Indian History*.15 June 2011. (<https://amirrorofindianhistory.blogspot.com>).
12. Pandey Anjali (2020): Orchha- The Architectural Heritage of Madhya Pradesh. *Int.Nat. Jour. of Research- Granthalaya*.Vol.8(4)pp.262-272.
13. Vakhariya SR and Bhagat SS (2020) : Proposal for one day tourist circuit in Orchha. Heritage Tourism. *Int. Nat. Res. Jour. of Engineering and Technology (IRJET)* Vol. 7(5)pp.6804-6808.(www.irjet.net).